

Short name	Helsinki Convention	Long name	Convention on the Protection of the Marine Environment of the Baltic Sea Area
Geographical scope	Baltic Sea area		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	The Helsinki Convention prohibits all dumping in the Baltic Sea area, with the exception of dredged material (which is subject to a prior special permit issued by the appropriate national authority in accordance with the provisions of Annex V). Thus, on the face of it, storage of CO ₂ is prohibited in the BSR as CO ₂ is not explicitly included as an exception. An amendment is likely going to be required to allow geological storage of CO ₂ .		
Key examples where this issue manifests (also based on stakeholder inputs)	Storage is prohibited in the Convention area (Baltic Sea Area), which for the purpose of the convention is the Baltic Sea and the entrance to the Baltic Sea bounded by the parallel of the Skaw in the Skagerrak at 57° 44.43'N. It includes the internal waters, i.e., for the purpose of the convention waters on the landward side of the base lines from which the breadth of the territorial sea is measured up to the landward limit according to the designation by Contracting Parties. (article 1).		
Other issues this affects			
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HELCOM (2014): Convention on the Protection of the Marine Environment of the Baltic Sea Area, Link: https://helcom.fi/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/Helsinki-Convention_July-2014.pdf • Rütters, H. (2022): National and international legislation and regulations with respect to CO₂ geological storage, CO₂GeoNet Webinar, Link: http://www.co2geonet.com/media/76245/co2geonet-webinar_legislation_clear.pdf 		